

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B269
Date: 22 February 2007
Take Off: 10:30:36Z
Landing: 14:32:38Z
Flight Time: 4h02m02

Campaign: GFDEX – Icelandic Jet & Wake

Operating Area: Iceland S & E Coast

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Nina Peterson	UEA
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
7	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Bob Wells	FAAM
8	AVAPS	Stuart Heath	FAAM
9	Mission Scientist 2	Jon Egill Kristjansson	University of Oslo
10	Mission Scientist 3	Haruldur Olafson	Icelandic Met Office
11	Mission Scientist 4	Kent Moore	University of Toronto
12	Film Crew 1	Robert Nisbet	Sky News
13	Film Crew 2	David Rees	Sky News
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Flight Track:

B269 Track 22-FEB-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b269
 Date: 22 Feb 2007
 Project: GFDEX - Icelandic Jet & Wake
 Location: Iceland

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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091519		Start-Up	0.42 kft	054	63'59.65N, 22'37.66W
100829		INU	0.42 kft	054	To Navigate
102456		ASPs	0.42 kft	195	Open
103036		T/O	1.3 kft	090	Keflavik
103715		Videos	1.8 kft	346	Start FFC & DFC
104040	104649	Run 1	1.8 kft	135	A - B
104650	104728	Profile 1	1.8 - 2.3 kft	131	1.5k' to 2k', Q1001
104728	105011	Run 2	2.3 kft	132	2k'
105011	105414	Profile 2	2.3 - 6.3 kft	124	2k' to 6k'
105414	112601	Run 3	6.3 kft	128	6k'
112757	113620	Profile 3	6.3 - 2.4 kft	313	6k' to 2k', 500fpm
113620	115215	Run 4	2.4 kft	328	QNH1000, C-B
115407	115605	Profile 4	2.4 - 1.4 kft	121	2k - 1k', 500fpm 1k'
115606	122512	Run 5	1.4 kft	117	1k' , B - new C
120738		Videos	1.4 kft	120	Change Tapes
121747		Heimann	1.4 kft	121	Cal
122643	122840	Profile 5	1.4 - 3.4 kft	050	From 1k', C-D
123046	125224	Profile 5	3.4 - 25.0 kft	052	From 3k'
125224	132344	Run 6	25.0 kft	049	
132221		Sonde	25.0 kft	257	Launch #01, no winds
132424	132559	Profile 6	25.0 - 24.5 kft	248	P6
133430		Sonde	25.0 kft	250	Launch #02
133845	134128	Profile 7	25.0 - 24.0 kft	248	
134051		Videos	24.2 kft	248	Change Tapes
134129	141729	Run 7	24.0 - 24.1 kft	247	
143238		Land	0.47 kft	157	Keflavik
144147		Shutdown	0.47 kft	254	63'58.45N, 22'35.78W

B269 Track 22-FEB-07

GFDex Sortie Brief – 22st February 2007 – Icelandic jet and wake

Mission Scientist 1 – G. Nina Petersen

Mission Scientists – Haraldur Olafsson, Jon Egill Kristjansson, Kent Moore

Observers: Sky News Crew

Aims

- Map out 3-D structure of the jet along the southern coast of Iceland in stably stratified easterly flow.
- Measure the wake behind (west of) Iceland
- Dropsonde east of Iceland to describe the unperturbed upstream flow.

GFD13	Time	Manoeuvre	Distance (nm)	Duration (min)	Total time (min)
1	10.30	Take off Keflavík, climb to 1500ft, and then a straight level run to to 64°30N 22°40W.		10	10
2	10.40	Climbing from 1500ft to 6000ft flying from 64°30N 22°40W to 63°50N 21°W, approaching land.		15	25
3	10.55	Straight level run at 6000ft from 63°50N 21°W to 63°N 19°W.		20	45
4	11.15	Descend to 2000ft, turn 180° flying from to 63°N 19°W back to 63°50N 21°W.		25	70
5	11.40	Descend to 500ft, turn 180°, flying from 63°50N 21°W back to 63°N 19°W, perhaps slightly farther if not out of jet core.		25	95
6	12.05	Profile climbing to 25,000ft, flying from 63°N 19°W to 64°20N 14°W		40	135
7	1245	Straight level run at 25,000ft from 64°20N 14°W to 65°40N 12°W.		20	155
8	13.05	Dropsonde at 65°40N 12°W and then transit back to Keflavik.		55	210
10	14.00	Land in Keflavik			

Mission Scientists Debriefing Sheet

Flight No. B269

Date: 22.02. 2007

Sortie Objectives: Map out the 3-D structure of the jet along the southern coast of Iceland in stable stratified easterly (*and northeasterly?*) flow as well as the wake in the lee of the island (to the west). One dropsonde upstream to measure the upstream conditions.

Summary of weather conditions: Easterly flow with flow distortion around Iceland. To the south there is a jet as the flow is forced to the left as it impinges upon the island. To the west there is a wake with light winds.

Flight Pattern: From Keflavik at 1500ft straight to the north, to 64°30N 22°40W (point A). Turned to the southeast, a straight profile at 1500ft climbing to 2000ft over Reykjavik and then 6000ft at 63°50N 21°W (point B). Straight level run towards past 63°N 19°W (point C) to 62°38N 18°30W (new C) to make sure we were out of the wake. Very low wind speeds in Faxafloi (to the north of Reykjanes Peninsula), down to 1 m/s. Over the southern part of the peninsula and to the south the visibility was poor, most likely due to salt. Winds off the southern coast, ~14 m/s 102°, but picking up slowly. Clouds 1-2/8 at 1000-1500ft, 6/8 at 5000ft. Clouds touching coast and cloud streets in lower cloud layer that we flew over. Turning and descending down to 2000ft. Straight level run back to point B. Two separate cloud layers. Large gradient in the wind field, outside the wake ~30 m/s but inside the wake ~7 m/s. Some turbulence in part of the wake even though horizontal wind speed was low. Descended down to 1000ft and did a straight level run out to new C. The original plan of 500ft was abandoned due to low visibility. Winds down to 2 m/s 6° in the wake but picking up and increased turbulence outside. In jet core, wind speed in core stable at ~29 m/s. This leg was below cloud base but it was quite misty. Upstream at 65°40N 12°W a sonde was released. It gave no wind data so another one was released. The dropsonde showed wind shear at about 600 hPa with westerly flow above but easterly below.

Assessment of the Flight: Overall a successful flight with the exception of the additional dropsonde release. Since turbulence measurements for flux calculations were not important, the 1000ft leg should give sufficiently good data.

Guðrún Nína Petersen

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B269** Date **22.02.07** Name **GNP** Page **1** of **2**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10.30					Take off
10.40	2				1500 ft. wind 7 m/s 184°
10.45					mountain waves over 2 picture
10.46.50					Climbing to 2000ft.
10.47.40	2				2000ft.
10.49.		2000ft.			10 m/s 82°
10.50	PR				profile to 6000ft.
					ended flying in the cloud tops ^{top} of thick clouds
11.00					low visib. below us
11.02		6000ft.			wind speed 14 m/s. 102° 1-2/8 at 1000-1500ft. 6/8 5000ft. clouds touching coast
11.08					cloud street in lower cloud layer
11.09					flying over the lower clouds
11.13					wind increasing slowly 100°
11.25				6203844N 1803081W	turning and descending to 2000ft descending 300 ft/min towards C 2 main ^{separate} cloud layers high ^{top 500} + 4800
11.30					wavy tops of clouds

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B26a** Date **22.02** Name **GNP** Page **2** of **2**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11.34					still descending pas C
11.36.20		2000ft			
11.47					(inside wake w w 7 m/s but bumpy but bumpy
11.52.50					desc. to 1000ft. ^{scott} ps. minute
11.54.07		1000ft			
11.55					winds down to 2 m/s 6°
11.56.06		1000ft			
12.00					wind picking up + turb.
12.01					in jet core 22 m/s 81°
12.05					misty but under cldbase
12.06					77kt increasing 90°
12.20					unstable core at ~29 m/s
12.25.12					ascend point C (new)
12.26.43	5				profile to 3000ft
12.28.40		3000ft.			
12.30.46					profile to 25.000ft,
13.16					cloud cur breaking up <small>small, tooish cumulus clouds broken stratocumulus no high clouds alto stratocumulus</small>
					From dropsonde
					cloud tops at 1900m ~2000ft
					Wind speed incr. at same level
					& slight inversion, dry above
					wind shear w-ly at 600 hPa E-ly below

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG B269

Flight No. B269

Date: 22/02/07

Operator: KFT

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G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	
10:40:42	178	0.08	1	-	0	0		0	0		Start R1 1500FT at point A
10:46:50	87	0.08	1	-	0	0		0	0		End R1
10:47:30	160	0.07	1	-							Start R2 at 2KFT
10:50:11	153	0.07	1	-							End R2, start P2
10:51:05	160	0.08	1	-	0	0		0	0		FL030
10:51:50	48.9	0.10	1	-	0	0		0	0		FL040
10:52:50	61	0.08	1	-	0	0		0	0		FL050
10:53:31	48	0.07	1	-	0	0		0	0		FL060
10:56:00	54	0.06	1	-	0	0		0	0		R3 at 6KFT`
11:00:00	40	0.08	1	-	0	0		0	0		
11:03:00	44	0.06	1	-	0	0		0	0		
11:05:00	40	0.07	1	-	0	0		0	0		
11:10:00	51	0.06	2	-	0	0		0	0		
11:15:00	38	0.07	2	-	0	0		0	0		
11:20:00	48	0.07	2	-	0	0		0	0		FFSSP Base offsets increased
11:26:02	73	0.07	4	-	0	0		0	0		End R3
11:27:58	68	0.08	5	-	0	0		0	0		Start P3 at 6KFT
11:30:55	47	0.07	9	-	0	0		0	0		FL050
11:31:50	51	0.06	217	-	3	200	4,8,11	0	0		FL047 cloud top
11:33:40	421	0.19	1300	-	35	225	8,11	175	800	8	FL040
11:35:25	364	0.12	2694	-	95	300	8,11	675	800	8	FL030
11:36:19	115	0.09	2848	-	13.5	300	8,11	33	800	8	FL020 START RUN4
11:40:00	170	0.12	2899	-	20.5	300	8,11	33	800	8	CIP disk full – PC crash
11:45:00	309	0.27	2993	-	0	0		0	0		
11:50:00	126	0.18	3150	-	0	0		0	0		
11:52:14	161	0.17	3223	-	0	0		0	0		End Run4
11:54:07	126	0.23	3317	-	0	0		0	0		Start P4
11:56:07	169	0.23	3412	-	0	0		0	0		End P4 Start R5 at 1000FT
11:57:00	170	0.21	3522	-	10	100	8,11	0	0		
12:00:00	199	0.21	3888	-	0	0		0	0		
12:03:00	135	0.16	4410	-		50	8,11	0	0		
12:05:00	111	0.17	4822	-	1.5	200	8,11	0	0		
12:08:00	162	0.18	5589	-	3	125	8,11	0	0		Voltages on FFSSP awry!
12:10:00	256	0.26	6323	-	3.5	300	8,11	0	0		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG B269

Flight No. B269

Date: 22/02/07

Operator: KFT

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
12:12:00	120	0.12	6583	-	3.5	400	8,11,1	33	400	8	
12:15:00	192	0.11	6985	-	7	400	1,8,11	8	400	8	
12:18:00	140	0.10	7571	-	2.5	400	1,11,8	0	0		
12:20:00	105	0.11	8198	-	1	100	11,8,1	0	0		
12:22:00	137	0.11	8770	-	2.5	100	11,8	0	0		
12:25:14	124	0.10	8770	-	3	100	11,8	17	200	8	End R4
12:26:42	120	-.10	8770	-	0.5	100	11,8	0	0		Start P5
12:21:20	208	0.09	8770	-	12	300	11,8	0	0		FL020
12:28:17	50	0.09	8770	-	9.5	800	5,8,4	25	800	5	FL030 FFSSP frozen.
12:31:30	305	0.18	119	-	10	200	8,11	0	0		FL040
12:32:30	18	0.06	185	-	0	0		0	0		FL050
12:34:20	8	0.07	224	-	0	0		0	0		FL070
12:35:20	15	0.06	224	-	0	0		0	0		FL080
12:36:20	140	0.11	224	-	6	800	4,11,5	680	800	8	FL090
12:37:20	11	0.06	225	-	8	800	4,11,5	700	800	8,5	FL100
12:38:18	9	0.07	225	-	8	800	4,5	700	1200	8	FL110
12:39:20	5	0.20	226	-	14	800	4,5,11	1450	1200	8	FL120
12:40:20	11	0.26	227	-	23	800	4,5,11	2266	1200	8	FL130
12:41:20	23	0.27	229	-	13	800	4,5,11	1500	1200	8	FL140
12:42:20	9	0.07	229	-	8	800	4,5,8	1158	1000	8	FL150
12:43:20	16	0.10	230	-	9	800	4,8	1175	800	8	FL160
12:44:20	25	0.13	230	-	9	800	4,8	2408	800	8	FL170
12:45:20	22	0.13	231	-	11	625	4,8	2233	800	8	FL180
12:46:20	17	0.05	231	-	11	700	8,4	2750	700	8	FL190
12:47:20	11	0.35	232	-	32	350	8,5	3891	400	8	FL200
12:48:20	45	0.06	233	-	41	325	8	9366	200	8	FL210
12:49:20	194	0.15	234	-	27	350	8	5808	350	8	FL220
12:50:20	5	0.30	235	-	20	325	8,4	9608	325	8	FL230
12:51:20	8	0.32	235	-	19	275	8,5	41066	-		Noise ON 2dp (MS38)
12:52:20	2	0.06	236	-	12	275	8,4	-	-	-	FL250 end P5 NOISE on 2DP
13:05:00	5	0.30	238	-	107	150	8,11	-	-	-	
13:10:00	11	0.07	243	-	0	0	8,11	0	0		
13:15:00	13	0.06	243	-	0	0		0	0		
13:22:20	4	0.09	243	-	0	0		0	0		NOISE on 2DP, Sonde 1 dropped

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B269 **T/O:** 10:30:36
Date of flight: 22/02/7 **Land:** 14:32:38

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		To Exeter
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B269
Date of Flight: 22/02/07

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	15510 blocks
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 193283
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 39143 Blocks written = 39143 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N		Start = 103000 End = 143000 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Y Are they non-zero in size? Y
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images Noise from 125000 on 2DP Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 103000 End = 140000 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	Y	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X = A</p> <p>Start = 103000 End = 143000</p> <p>Time data processed to = 135618.8 2dproc files present? Y *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	Y	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored. Records = 4050, 178</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	Y	<p>X = A Y = (X+1) = B</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	Y	<p>Correlated? Y</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B269
Date of Flight: 22/02/07

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Min size = 1 Vol flow rate = 1.15 103000 143000
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = B Y = X+1 = C
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	Y	Merged OK?Y

Flight:

B269

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

**Report Created 15/03/2007
12:11:09**

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

14/03/2007 15:54:52

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B269

Date: 22 Feb 2007

Instruments

1. FFC window dirty
2. CO – suspect initial cal, only got up to around 500ppb
3. SID1 – no data. Probe/pc not communicating.
4. Satcom C – stopped sending position reports in flight. Message
“H_SATCOM 22-FEB-07 11:43:17 SATCOM - Command read error: 1 556 0 0
H_SATCOM 22-FEB-07 11:43:17 Satcom not responding - -3”
In h_satcom.log and “Satcom hardware status unavailable” on HORACE satcom menu Option 5
Tried resetting CB and stop / start h_satcom, no change.
5. CPC – reading 0 counts on HORACE although counts displayed on CPC. Found data cable had disconnected at CPC end.

Aircraft

Satcom-H Calls

- 1 call – FAAM
- 1 call - DFL

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 22/2/07

Flight No: B269

Pre-Flighter: AMW

<u>Item</u>	<u>√ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	- N/A ICE APPLIED, FOLD CHECKED. WIPED GELS NOT CLEANED
<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All reqd CBs made	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	n/a
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			

External Checks overleaf →

4160
 4200
 1960
 1900
 12220
 124570
 10750
 13
 28
 104

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u>	<u>✓ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	<i>WHERE POSSIBLE</i>
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				Signed
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		<i>[Signature]</i>
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Traps empty (weekly only)		
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<i>HEAT PROS REMOVED.</i>		

Flight B269 12:53:52

Heading 49 deg Speed 328 knots Height 25.0kft Press 375mb

Lat 63°54.0'N Long 15°6.0'W Wind 8 ms-1/ 235 deg

Temp -39.44C Dewpoint -41.12C

From 12:26:35 to now

Current values

STATIC PRESSURE

375.54

mb

++++ DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP

-39.44

deg C

++++ DEW POINT

-41.16

deg C

Flight B269 14:35:10

Heading 158 deg Speed 25 knots Height 0.4kft Press 996mb

Lat 63°54.0'N Long 22°30.0'W Wind 4 ms-1/ 79 deg

Temp 1.84C Dewpoint -6.75C

From 14:11:34 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	996.09	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	1.85	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	-6.76	deg C

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B269:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	20 Mar 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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Daily weather summary 22 February 2007

<p>Large scale situation today:</p>	<p>A 960 hPa low pressure 54N 30W with a second low at its periphery of it to the east. A high pressure system of 1041 hPa is located over northern Sweden and Finland. Just south-southeast of Newfoundland is a 933 hPa low moving east and a 991 hPa low at the coast of Labrador. A mesoscale cyclone of 1005 hPa is located east of Iceland at about 0W. (Based on UKMO analysis from 06Z)</p>
<p>Features of interest:</p>	<p>The winds are still easterly impinging upon Iceland resulting in a jet to the south and a wake to the west. There is indication of large fluxes in the jet. There are still strong northeasterlies over the Irminger Sea with acceleration at Cape Farewell. The mesoscale cyclone is outside of reach but still interesting. A nice comma cloud is associated with it.</p> <div data-bbox="359 757 1222 1330" style="text-align: center;"> <p>Analysis chart valid 06 UTC Thu 22 FEB 2007</p> </div>
<p>Action:</p>	<p>A flight is planned: The Icelandic shadow – or wake and jet flight.</p>
<p>Outlook for the next 24-48 hours:</p>	<p>The flow is dominated by the cyclones over the North Atlantic. The large scale cyclone moves eastward and is located at about 58N 19W in the 48h forecast. The other two cyclones move eastward and merge together after about 42h. The merged cyclone is located at 56N 32W in the 48h forecast. The high pressure system has moved farther south. The mesoscale cyclones moves north of 70N and starts to move westward. The pressure in the centre is 1004 hPa.</p> <p>(The ECMWF forecast doesn't show the same merging of the two smaller cyclones but rather that they fill. However, the forecast available has 24h between charts which makes it difficult to interpret the evolution)</p>
<p>Outlook for the next 48-96 hours:</p>	<p>The second cyclone catches up with the more developed one and they circle together for 24 hours as they fill, the older one moves north and has become a trough in the 96h forecast while the other low moves eastward over the UK and is just east of the UK at 988 hPa in the 96h forecast.</p>

MSLP for T+24 DT 200702251200 VT 200702261200 no bal main NWP
Level 500 Geopotential Height for T+24 DT 200702251200 VT 200702261200 ukmo global main NWP

MSLP for T+39 DT 200702241200 VT 200702260300 ukmo nae main NWP
level 500 Geopotential Height for T+39 DT 200702241200 VT 200702260300 ukmo nae main NWP

MSLP for T+45 DT 200702241200 VT 200702260900 ukmo nae main NWP
Level 500 Geopotential Height for T+45 DT 200702 200 VT 200702260900 ukmo nae main NWP

